

Teacher F. B. Ševčík and his lecture for the Mathematisches Damen-Collegium

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Abstract

This brief paper looks back at teacher F. B. Ševčík and the rare initiative focused on female education that took place in Vienna in the nineteenth century. Mathematics lectures for women were organized in the frame of the *Mathematisches Damen-Collegium*. Motivation lecture focused on the importance of mathematics prepared by teacher F. B. Ševčík is being presented.

Keywords: mathematics education; female education; Vienna

1 Introduction

František Bedřich Ševčík (1824 Jedovnice – 1896 Vienna) was popular mathematics teacher, musician and singer who interacted with renown mathematicians Joseph Salomon and Joseph Petzval. He took part in public life as member of the Union of Czech mathematicians and physicists, the Komenský School Association in Vienna and the Patriotic Museum Society in Olomouc. Ševčík enjoyed travelling through Europe, keeping notes during his journeys and documenting his interest in education and music. He had a spirit of philanthropy donating books to schools as educational support.

The story of Ševčík can be summarized based on biography book written in Czech language by Horňanský (1898) [1]. Ševčík started his education in Jedovnice, continuing at main school in Brno. There he completed a course on pedagogy receiving qualification as school teacher assistant. In 1842, Ševčík moved to Vienna and studied at the k.k. Polytechnisches Institut undertaking wide range of subjects, e.g. arithmetic, higher mathematics, physics, mineralogy, agronomy. He also visited a singing school at Vienna Conservatory. From 1851 to 1853, Ševčík helped with mathematics teaching at the k.k. Polytechnisches Institut. In 1854, he passed the state exam for teachers

in mathematics and chemistry. He taught mathematics at multiple schools in Vienna. Ševčík improved his mathematics qualification by visiting lectures of Joseph Petzval and Josef Stefan at the University of Vienna as show certificates with their signatures from the archive in Olomouc. At the instigation of the professor Joseph Petzval, Ševčík got a habilitation as Privatdozent for the mathematical theory of tone systems and taut strings.

Short summary of arithmetic by F. B. Ševčík is given in textbook [2], which quantitative part begins with arithmetic teaching text named *Kurze Wiederholung aus der Arithmetik*. The idea of including basic mathematics fundamentals in textbook dealing with quantitative chemical analysis is quite fitting not only for the environment of the 19th century. It enabled students to repeat and broaden their arithmetic skills without the need of further literature. Similar attitude could be useful also nowadays, even in time of easy access to information. It has to be said that his explaining of arithmetic using many examples is illustrative.

The personal fund of F. B. Ševčík, in the archive of the Regional museum in Olomouc, contains original mathematics teaching preparations, arranged according to specific areas of mathematics, works of his students, notes taken during his traveling in Europe and unpublished lecture for the *Mathematisches Damen-Collegium*.

2 Lecture for *Mathematisches Damen-Collegium*

The *Mathematisches Damen-Collegium* was organized by Ševčík in Vienna from 1974. Horňanský (1898) reports almost 685 students were educated during six years. Remarkable for 19th century education system.

We can have a closer look at the *Damen-Collegium* thanks to the lecture notes of Ševčík. Text is in handwritten German with few Latin formulations. Twenty single pages manuscript was recognized from the old handwritten Kurrent with the help of *Transkribus* software platform for automatic handwriting text recognition. This lecture was most probably presented in the front of the audience. Brief synopsis of the lecture follows.

Lecture links mathematics historically to the advances in culture and education. At the beginning, Ševčík says he wants only to describe, without any overstatement, what are the good things about mathematics. Mathematics is described as indisputably one of the most beautiful, important and beneficial inventions of human intellect. Lecture continues: Mathematics has direct and indirect ways to contribute endlessly to the progress of the culture and the general intellectual education. Already the rudiments of the first mathematical elements were connected to the needs of an ordinary life. Mathematics helps better understand and consider usual life. Many discoveries and fields of science wouldn't exist without mathematics: Practical counting (arithmetic), geodesy, statics, mechanics, hydrostatics, hydrodynamics, hydraulics, aerometry, optics, catoptrics, dioptrics, perspective, photometry, astronomy, geography, chronology, gnomonics, civil engineering, hydraulic engineering, road construction, shipbuilding, artillery (as military science), pyrotechnics and military engineering (fortification). As Ševčík summarizes, the knowledge of an engineer is

everywhere so close to the knowledge of a mathematician that it is not needed to clarify the value of mathematics for engineering anymore.

Lecture proceeds: The historian appreciates mathematics in connection with its daughter astronomy because of reliable determination of years in history to remote past. Mathematics shows to the medical doctors trusted law: It guides them through number and measure of the vegetative life conditions, helps to predict how many living beings are going to be born or to die in certain district. Mathematics is not less important for the judicious statesman whose task is the support of advancement of all forces of the state in the harmonic and the best possible manner. Mathematics shows the way in the form of statistics in order to achieve such goal with lowest possible losses of time and capital. It teaches him how flourishing of the state is linked to certain unchangeable natural conditions that have to be inevitably respected. Mathematics leads to the appropriate governance. Since mathematics, after just heard discussion, is deeply involved in all relations of civil life, mathematics deserves appreciation and cautious care of every educated state.

Lecture continues with a look into the past. It mentions that mathematics is so old as an education of human altogether and includes former mathematicians and philosophers Thales of Miletus, Pythagoras of Samos, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz and Archimedes of Syracuse. Afterwards, lecture mentions meaning of mathematics for logic as it gives wonderful collection of examples for the logician. Text describes mathematical activities being amazing as gymnastics for the brain and balancing fantasy with intellect. Ševčík concludes lecture with the statement how happy he is to be the first mathematics teacher for the students of the *Mathematisches Damen-Collegium*. That's the end of the synopsis of the lecture with its parts translated in contextual translation.

3 Conclusion

In spite of the fact that F.B. Ševčík was mainly active in the area of mathematics, presented lecture shows his interdisciplinary approach to his teaching. The spillovers into other fields are frequent.

Preserved lecture apparently served as a motivation for study of mathematics and is interesting from the educational point of view. Isn't such a complex approach in teaching appropriate even today? It would be good not to forget this initiative from the 19th century, which belongs to pioneering initiatives in terms of female education in Europe.

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Declarations

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References

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